

PROGRESS OF PROGRex: A COMPACT X-RAY/GAMMA-RAY SPECTROMETER FOR THE HARLOCK PROJECT. F. Fiore¹, G. Baroni¹, R. Campana¹, M. Citossi¹, A. Černok^{1,2}, F. Dogo¹, Y. Evangelista⁴, T. Fagotto^{1,2}, C. Feruglio¹, N. Sesto Gorella¹, S. Trevisan^{1,3} (sara.trevisan@unitn.it), A. Trois¹, and F. Pedichini¹

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Summary: X-ray and gamma-ray spectroscopy can be used to assess the composition of planetary surfaces, which is a key ingredient for both studying the body origin and evolution and prospecting for its resources. PROGRex (Prospecting the Moon with Gamma & X-rays) is an X-ray and gamma-ray spectrometer derived from the instrument developed for the SpIRIT and HERMES Pathfinder projects. The unit on board SpIRIT, a 6U CubeSat managed by University of Melbourne, has been working on Low Earth Orbit since January 2024, and thus reached TRL9.

PROGRex is also a part of the strategic project HARLOCK (High-resolution Autonomous Resource Lunar Observation & Characterization Kit, [1]) of the initiative "Il PROgramma di RIcerca Spaziale di base (PRORIS; www.proris.it) funded by the Italian Ministry of Universities and Research (MUR). The main goal of HARLOCK is to bridge the gap on the Moon surface composition of metals and REE between the several tens km scale allowed by the best remote sensing observations (e.g. Kaguya), and sample return sites (e.g. Apollo, Chang'e). Hierarchical in situ exploration strategy for REEs includes Gamma-ray spectroscopy, which provides a first-order geochemical survey and proxy mapping, followed by hyperspectral VIS-NIR hyperspectral imaging and UV-induced fluorescence screening to identify REE-enriched outcrops. Positive detections are then investigated at close range by X-ray spectroscopy.

PROGRex covers in a single instrument the very broad band from about 1 keV to about 3 MeV. This allows both gamma-ray spectroscopy of nuclear lines such as K, Th, U with a moderate resolution of 6% at 600keV, and X-ray spectroscopy of atomic lines with a resolution of 150-200 eV. The X-ray band covers fluorescence emission of elements from Si to Ti, Fe, Ni, REEs and the PGEs. Therefore, the same spectrometer can be exploited for remote and in-situ observations. For the HARLOCK project in-situ application, a rover will be equipped with both a gamma-ray payload to search for nuclear lines and an X-ray fluorescence source, to search for atomic lines from rocks and regolith.

Figure 1: Heritage from SpIRIT and HERMES Pathfinder projects, photo detector, SDD scintillator crystal GAGG covering from a few keV to a few MeV $\geq 50 \text{ cm}^2$ collimated area.

Goal: functional test on proper lunar environment by the end of third year. Added values: (1) bring TRL to 9; (2) test of planned operations; (3) test of observations of real lunar materials.

Description of activities: PROGRex is designed as a three-year project. It is divided into two main stages, aiming to reach following milestones:

- 1) End of first year, breadboards to demonstrate main technologies: TRL 5
- 2) End of third year: Demonstration Models, to demonstrate full functionality in proper environment, considering interfaces with Rover (thermal, electric, electronics, informatics) TRL7-9

Each demonstration model (DM) should be representative of main functionalities of the instrument and conceived to be able to function on a rover, e.g. it should be compliant with interfaces.

- Survive one lunar day
- Rover: NDA signed with iSpace and Lunar Outpost, discussions already on going with them on interfaces and accommodation
- MVP: Functional and environmental tests on ground (mechanical, TVAC).

Ongoing activities include Monte Carlo simulations of XRF measurements under different geometries, illumination conditions, and target compositions, together with the preparation of laboratory measurements on rock samples representative of the lunar composition, to support the future development of PROGRex.

The management of the HARLOCK strategic project was assigned to CNR and INAF as part of the collaboration between the two institutions on research programmes, technological developments and training. PROGRex team includes the following institutions: INAF, University of Trieste, University of Pavia, Politecnico of Milano, and the Bruno Kessler Foundation.

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